

TEXTILE REINFORCED CONCRETE COMPOSITE FOR ADVANCED CONSTRUCTION APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Textile Reinforced Concrete (TRC) is an innovative composite material that possesses excellent properties including ease of manufacturing, highly compatible to other existing inorganic-based construction materials and most importantly fire resistant which offers a potential material for building facades. Textiles such as glass, carbon, basalt are used as the internal reinforcement in a thin concrete matrix to form TRC. In TRC, the matrix fails before the tensile capacity of the fibres is reached. Fibres will help to bridge the cracks formed in the matrix, thus improving the serviceability capacity and limiting the crack width. This research investigated, for the first time, the behaviour of high-performance textile reinforced concrete (HSTRC) with different mixes and reinforced configuration. The HSTRC samples were also exposed to different elevated temperatures to examine its response to flexural deflection. Results showed that the layers of reinforced textile improved the flexural strength by 28% while the exposure to elevated temperature significantly affected HSTRC flexural strength. Further investigation on the interfacial bonding between the reinforcing textile and the cementitious matrix at elevated temperature is recommended.

1 INTRODUCTION

Textile Reinforced Concrete (TRC) is an innovative product formed from a combination of cementitious matrix and usually a 2D textile fabric [1]. Last few years, TRC has emerged as an efficient construction material. It has many advantages such as light-weight, strength, stiffness etc. [2-5]. However, the applications are limited due to lack of basic understanding of the failure mechanisms, material properties and design methods.

TRC can be used to build different types of structural components and systems due to its versatile forming capabilities. It can be easily adapted to complex free-form geometries and produce slender and thin components with complicated shapes. Usual metallic reinforcement requires significant cover to the reinforcement and similar TRC members can be made very thin due to the elimination of the risk of corrosion. TRC also provides high strength in compression and tension. TRC not only can be used for new structures but is suitable for the strengthening of existing structures. The reduction of cement volume will make it an environmentally sustainable building material with low embodied energy compared to conventional concrete.

Depending on the performance requirements, TRC has the flexibility to be designed for each application [6,7]. In TRC the textile fabric can be changed using different type of yarns and geometry. Advanced manufacturing techniques have allowed a wide variety of fabrics to be produced and control the yarn geometry and orientation. A high-performance cementitious mix can also be designed to obtain the required strength and other properties such as low shrinkage, low permeability, etc. Different type of sustainable admixtures such as fly ash, slag, micro-silica can be used to replace the cement. Nano-engineered composites with nano-silica, carbon nano tubes, etc. can be added if

required [8]. Currently, the authors have also been looking at graphene as a possible high-value addition to improve the properties.

An overview of developments in last decade in TRC composites will be given in the presentation including the work done by the authors on engineered material development, identification of performance requirements and multi-scale modelling techniques to achieve essential properties such as strength and ductility. It is very important to have multiple cracking upon loading in concrete structures. TRC not only outperforms conventional concrete in this regard, but in addition reduces the crack width. The polymer-based composite failure is due to fibre rupture followed by the failure of the matrix. However, in cement composites, the matrix fails before the tensile capacity of the fibres is reached. Fibres will help to bridge the cracks formed in the matrix, thus improving the serviceability capacity and limiting the crack width.

1.1 Applications of TRC in prefabricated structures

Many applications in construction can be found in TRC. They range from TRC building façade panels, permanent formwork, 3D-shaped architectural elements, bridges, shell structures, and even in tunneling and other infrastructure. TRC can also be incorporated into a structure as an external layer to provide extra strength and improve durability, impact resistance etc.

Authors have been exploring possible applications of TRC in prefabricated building construction. They can be categorized as follows according to the way it is manufactured and assembled on site;

1. Modular (Volumetric) construction: Production of three-dimensional units including finishes in controlled factory conditions prior to transportation to site.

2. Panelised construction: Flat panel units are produced in a factory and assembled on-site to produce a three-dimensional structure. Structural Insulated Panels (SIPs) technologies have been developed to reduce the construction time and improve quality. An example is given in Fig.1. Thin TRC panels can be utilized as a sandwich element. Sandwich panels are very efficient providing very high strength-to-weight and stiffness-to-weight ratios. The skin mainly provides the strength and stiffness to carry the loads and the core carries some shear stresses and provides a thermal barrier and improve the acoustic performance. TRC is the skin and materials such as expanded polystyrene (EPS) or foam concrete can be used as the core.

Figure 1: A House constructed with SIP Panels [9]

1.2 Fire Performance of TRC facades

Engineers and Architects have been looking at building facades as a key application of TRC due to its obvious ability to form complex geometries and produce thin panels. Glass curtain-wall façades became preferable in contemporary architecture in last few decades due to its superiority in transmitting light and aesthetic appearance. However alternative “greener” materials like fibre

reinforced polymer composites (FRPCs) are considered now [10,11]. Lower weight and higher strength are two critical key properties that make FRPC “greener” than aluminium and steel. However, the fire resistance is an important issue as FRPC is sensitive to elevated temperatures and the failure of the composite structure should be studied comprehensively to ensure the safety of the occupants in fire incidents. TRC is a superior fire-resistant alternative to FRP facades to meet the available standards for building materials. It is non-combustible and will not contribute fuel to the spread of a fire.

2 EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

A detailed test programme was conducted to determine the flexural behaviour of HSTRC samples at ambient and elevated temperatures. The exposure to elevated temperatures was utilised to determine the applicability of HSTRC for building facades in different fire scenarios. The main two materials involved in the test program was, high strength concrete (HSC) and glass fibre textile. Considering the thinner section of TRC, it is important to have higher stiffness and higher strength in order to increase the capacity of the TRC samples considering flexural capacity required for wind and impact loadings.

2.1 Material Properties

Fine grained HSC mortar was used in the experiment to increase the workability and the self-compaction of the concrete. Maximum fine aggregate size was selected to be 1 mm to allow the concrete matrix to easily flow through the grids of the textile. Coarse aggregates were not used in concrete mix as concrete mix was required to flow through the grids of the textile with an aperture of 10 mm thickness and considering the overall thickness of the sample-16 mm. Commercially available superplasticizer (high-range water reducing) was used to reduce the water-to-binder ratio to a value of 0.25 thus increasing the 28-days compressive strength of concrete while retaining the high workability of the concrete. A commercially available viscosity modifier was used to increase the viscosity of fresh concrete for reducing the segregation and bleeding occurring in the concrete. The mix design for the HSC is shown in Table 1. Compressive tests were carried out on 7 days and 28 days to find the compressive strength of HSC mortar per ASTM C39 / C39M – 18 [12]. It was found that compressive strength of HSC concrete of 7 and 28 days were 74.5 MPa and 100 MPa, respectively.

Material	Cement (GP)	Sand	Fly Ash	Silica Fume	Slag	Water	Super-plasticizer	Viscosity Modifier	Retarder
Content (kg/m ³)	783	705	258	78	282	287	11	2	4

Table 1: Composition of concrete matrix

Uses and demand for glass fibres in mechanical and construction engineering are increasing due to the wide range of superior properties they possess. Higher-strength to weight ratio and resistance to corrosion of glass fibres dominate other common construction materials such as steel. In this study, glass fibres were used in the form of a textile with having yarns in two perpendicular directions (Fig. 1). The glass textile was consisted of 10 mm x 10 mm grids with material properties given in Table 2. The thickness of glass fibre was 0.5 mm in both directions.

Figure 1: Glass textile used in experiments

Mesh size (mm x mm)	Tensile load bearing capacity of 50 mm strip (N)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elastic modulus (GPa)	Ultimate strain
10 × 10	1800	1833	73	0.025

Table 2: Properties of glass textile

2.2 Preparation of specimens

In this study, HSTRC samples were prepared with dimensions of 320 mm length, 50 mm width and 16 mm thickness in accordance with ASTM D 7264/7264M [13]. Three identical samples were prepared to be tested in same experimental case.

Plastic moulds were used to cast HSTRC samples, and steel bolts were used to set the mould and hold the textile without sagging. HSTRC samples were prepared with one to three textile layers embedded in the HSC matrix through the thickness as shown in Fig. 2. The textile was placed to have warp yarns along the longitudinal direction of HSTRC sample. Textile was cut into pieces, larger than the actual specimen size to properly fit it into the mould. Concrete mortar was poured into the moulds. The fresh TRC sample was subjected to mechanical vibration until all the air bubbles trapped inside the concrete was released. Then sample was placed on a level surface for 24 hours at room temperature (20 °C) for hardening. After the hardening, the sample was removed from the moulds and placed in a curing tank filled with water at 20 ± 1 °C until the test date. Samples were named as the following format: TRC-L2-300T-s1. The first term-TRC-stands for Textile Reinforced Concrete, second term-L2-stands for number of textile layers, third term-stands for temperature exposure, and the last term-s1-stands for the sample number. RT stands for room temperature.

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of cross-sectional view of TRC (units: mm)

2.3 Experimental program

In this study, the effect of number of textile layers and effect of high temperature exposure on the flexural strength of HSTRC was investigated. Up to three layers of textiles were used in the experimental program. Selected samples were exposed to 300 °C and 750 °C temperatures for 30 minutes before testing (Fig. 4). The furnace temperature was set to increase at a rate of 50°C/min and after the 30 minute exposure the sample was left cooled naturally to room temperature prior to further testing.

Figure 4: HSTRC exposed to elevated temperatures

2.4 Test setup

Four-point bending test was conducted to determine the flexural behavior of HSTRC samples. Constant displacement rate of 1 mm/min was applied according to the ASTM D 7264/7264M [13]. Instron testing machine was used to load the HSTRC samples with a load cell of 50 kN capacity. The load and flexural deflection of the specimen was recorded at one second intervals until the failure of specimen. Schematic diagram of loading arrangement and snapshot of loading setup is shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5: (a) Schematic diagram of loading arrangement (units: mm) (b) Test setup

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results obtained from the flexural test are listed in **Table 3**. Ultimate flexural stresses of HSTRC samples were calculated using equation 1.

$$\sigma = (P*l)/(b*h^3) \quad (1)$$

Where, σ is the ultimate flexural strength, P is the ultimate flexural load, l is the effective span of HSTRC sample, b is the width of sample and h is the thickness of the sample.

Specimen ID	No. of TRC layers	Temperature exposure (°C)	Ultimate Load (N)	Ultimate Flexural Strength (MPa)	Ultimate Deflection
TRC-L1-RT-s1	1	N/A	88.2	1.72	4.015
TRC-L1-RT-s2	1	N/A	146.7	2.87	4.624
TRC-L2-RT-s1	2	N/A	205.1	4.01	6.813
TRC-L2-RT-s2	2	N/A	304.8	5.95	5.441
TRC-L3-RT-s1	3	N/A	461.1	9.01	5.626
TRC-L3-RT-s2	3	N/A	431.1	8.42	8.056
TRC-L3-300T-s1	3	300	438.3	8.56	3.33
TRC-L3-300T-s2	3	300	329.8	6.44	4.226
TRC-L3-750T-s1	3	750	37.6	0.73	1.883
TRC-L3-750T-s2	3	750	21.4	0.42	1.952

Table 3: Summary of experiment results

3.1 Effect of the number of textile layers

Load versus deformation curve of HSTRC samples are given in **Fig. 6**. The ultimate load, deflection and flexural strength were listed in **Table 3**.

Figure 6: Load vs Deflection curve of specimens for different number of textile layers

Number of textile layers per specimen had significant effect on both ultimate flexural strength and the peak deflection. Average increase of 117% and 280% of ultimate flexural strength was observed when the number of textile layers increase from 1 layer to 2 and 3 layers, respectively. The HSTRC has shown linear stress- strain behavior in the initial loading conditions. After the first crack appearance in HSC, sudden drop was observed in load. Then, the load started to increase and reached

its ultimate value. The sudden drop due to the load bearing mechanism changing from HSC to textile layer after the cracking. The sudden drop of load was more visible in TRC-L1 samples compared to TRC-L3 samples. The use of higher number of textile layers, has decreased the time taken to shift the load bearing mechanism from HSC to textile after the first crack. Lack of prestressing of textile layer during the preparation of sample may be the cause for the two sudden drops in flexural behavior of TRC-L3-RT-s1 sample prior to it reaching the ultimate load. After it reached the ultimate load, the cracks in the all specimens started to widen while the load decreased rapidly. The behavior of all HSTRC samples were same with having higher number of cracks in TRC-L3 samples compared to TRC-L2 and TRC-L1 samples at room temperature.

3.2 Effects of elevated temperature

HSTRC samples were exposed to two different elevated temperatures (300 °C and 750 °C). Cracks had been propagated during the elevated temperature exposure as shown in Fig. 7.

Figure 7: Specimens after exposed to elevated temperature (a) 300 °C (TRC3-LT) (b) 750 °C (TRC3-HT)

Samples exposed to 750 °C had more cracks compared to the samples exposed to 300 °C. As shown in Fig. 7 (b) TRC-L3-750T samples had cracks on bottom and top surface of the specimen through the whole width. Severe delamination and increasing brittleness were observed at the textile layers which can be explained by the pyrolysis of the binder used in the reinforced textile. It is, thus, recommended that the interfacial bonding between the matrix and the reinforced mesh at elevated temperature to be further investigated. However, the TRC-L3-300T samples (Fig. 7 (a)) had comparatively less amounts of cracks within the specimens with no delamination between textile and the mortar. The textile itself was observed to be undamaged without any visible defects.

Figure 8: Load vs Deflection curve of specimens for different temperature exposure

The low temperature exposure (300 °C) did not have significant effect on flexural capacity of

specimens. The average ultimate strength of TRC-LT samples was reduced to 7.5 MPa from 8.7 MPa compared to 0.6 MPa of TRC-L3-750T samples. The reduction of ultimate strength was 14% and 94% for 300 °C and 750 °C temperature exposures, respectively. These results showed the applicability of using HSTRC in areas with moderate fire risk such as bushfire prone zones and fire rated inter-tendency walls. Owing to the importance of maintaining adequate bending resistance for façade panels with high height/thickness ratio, further investigation on the flexural strength of HSTRC at other temperatures between 300°C and 750°C is recommended.

3 CONCLUSIONS

A Total number of 10 HSTRC samples were prepared and tested. The flexural behavior of HSTRC samples with different number of textile layers and different temperature exposures were studied. The following conclusions were made:

1. Number of textile layers per specimen had significant effect on flexural behavior of HSTRC samples.
2. 280% increase in flexural strength and 58% increase in flexural deformation was observed with increasing the number of textile layers to three from one.
3. Severe surface cracks and delamination between textile and concrete was observed on the specimens exposed to 750°C temperature. However, the specimen exposed to 300°C had comparatively less surface cracks with no sign of delamination between concrete and textile.
4. Effect of elevated temperature exposure on flexural behavior of HSTRC samples were significant when it exposed to high temperature levels (750°C). Flexural strength of high temperature exposure (750 °C) samples were reduced by 94%. However, flexural strength of TRC3-LT samples was reduced by only 45%.
5. Further studies are required to find the effect of water/binder ratio of concrete matrix on flexural performance of HSTRC. More experiments are required to define the critical elevated temperature exposure on flexural behavior of HSTRC considering the type of the textile material and the behavior of HSC mortar subject to elevated temperature.

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